

LINGUISTIC COMPARISON OF GENDER CATEGORY IN THE ENGLISH, RUSSIAN AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

Barno Mukhtorova

teacher, PhD student,
English Department, FerSU

Mavluda Akbarova

Kh.Yakubova

4th year students
English Department, FerSU

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7900219>

Annotation. The central concept of this paper concerns various linguistic differences between the English, Russian, and Uzbek languages with regard to the concept of category gender. The article explains gender classification as a linguistic phenomenon and highlights specific variations between these three languages.

Key words: category, simplification, phenomena

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolaning asosiy g'oyasi ingliz, rus va o'zbek tillarida gender toifasi atamasidagi ba'zi lingvistik farqlar haqidadir. Maqolada gender atamasining lingvistik hodisa sifatida tasniflanishi tasvirlangan va bu uch til o'rtasidagi o'ziga xos farqlar ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: kategoriya, soddalashtirish, hodisa

Аннотация. Основная идея, лежащая в основе данной работы, заключается в некоторых языковых различиях термина категории род в английском, русском и узбекском языках. В статье описывается категоризация гендера как языкового явления и иллюстрируются специфические различия между этими тремя языками.

Ключевые слова: категория, упрощение, явления

Introduction

In general, gender is not considered as an indispensable part of English grammar. This category does not find regular morphological expression. The existence of gender in English as a grammatical category are denied by linguistic scholars and they consider that stress its purely semantic character. For instance, B.Ilyish, F.Palmer and E.Morokhovskaya emphasize that nouns have no category of gender in modern English.

However, other scholars, M.Blokh, J.Lyons admit the existence of category of gender. Prof. Blokh states that the category of gender in English is expressed with the help of the obligatory correlation of nouns with the personal pronouns of the third person. According to some linguistic scholars, Every noun belongs originally to one of the three classes (masculine, feminine or neuter) and each of

these classes has its own grammatical features related to the words endings and forms of modifiers (adjectives, pronouns etc.). A noun keeps its grammatical gender in all of its forms and never changes it. Owing to those rules in English and Russian languages, we try to contrast them with gender categorization of animal names of Uzbek language and analyze it in different system languages. Examples of use, we collected from the English literary fairy tales animal names can be classified as follows:

Original text	... and as the Lory positively refused to tell its age, there was no more to be said.
Russian version	...Лори твёрдо отказался ответить на вопрос, сколько же ему лет, и тем разговор был исперчан.
Uzbek version	... Lori uning(o'zining) yoshini so'rab aytilgan savolga javob berishni keskin rad etgandan so'ng, suhbatni davom ettirishga asos qolmadi.

In Carroll's work, all of these figures are represented by the pronoun IT (u), indicating that the specific type of creature is irrelevant in the English text. When translating into Uzbek, their identity can be easily determined by their name. However, the challenge in the Russian translation lies in the fact that these names are linked to individuals from traditional stories that were familiar to the original audience.

Original text	When the mouse heard this, it turned round and swam slowly back to her.
Russian version	Услыхав это, мышь повернулась и медленно поплыла назад.
Uzbek version	Sichqon buni eshitgach, burildi va unga qarab suzib ketdi.

In the example above, the term "Mouse" was interpreted as a female mouse, since there was no explicit indication in the text that it was a "male" mouse. The

most extensive set of illustrations belonged to the third category, where the original text utilized animal names to denote the pronoun "he," while the translated text used "он" [which is masculine in Russian] and "u" [which is neuter in Uzbek]. This category also had instances where the animal's natural gender corresponded with the grammatical gender of the translated word in the target language.

The Longman Grammar of Spoken and Written English presents an approach on the topic of gender in animals. The writers take into account spoken language and regard gender as "a category of lesser significance in English compared to numerous other languages".

The writers differentiate between two primary gender categories: personal and non-personal.

Personal/human	Example noun	pronoun
Masculine	Tom, a boy, the man	He
Feminine	Sue, a girl, the woman	She
Dual	a journalist, the doctor	He, She
Non-personal/Neuter	a house, a bird	It

The subsequent category comprises of instances, titles of creatures that were unable to be rescued in the "correct" manner, thus the word "men" in the English text was converted to "women" in the Russian text. In Uzbek language, the optimal approach is to utilize the neutral form of the word.

Original text	... and when you catch a tortoise , you must scoop him out of his shell with your paw.
Russian version	А если найдешь черепаху , выцарапай ее лапой из панциря
Uzbek version	Agar sen Toshbaqani uchratib qolsang, panjalaring bilan uni kosasidan uzib olib tashla.

As previously discussed, the gender classification of animal names can be translated differently in various languages. We can conclude from these examples:

1. During the process of translating animal names, it is crucial to account for the potential differences in gender categories between languages.
2. Utilizing animal names aids in conserving and conveniently comprehending all the traits of gender classification.
3. This is highly significant as the linguistic context given language unit and the circumstantial (cultural) milieu establish its structure and standards, and if disregarded, may result in an incomplete interpretation of the written work.

References:

1. Вежбицкая А. Язык. Культура. Познание. – М.: Русские словари, 1997. – 416 с.
2. ALEXANDER, L.G. 1991. Longman English Grammar Practice. Longman - LEGP
3. ALEXANDER, L.G. 1998. Longman English Grammar. Longman -LEG
4. BIBER, D. – JOHANSSON, S. – LEECH, G. – CONRAD, S. – FINEGAN, E. 1999.
5. Longman Grammar of Spoken and Written English. London: Longman.
6. VACHEK, J. 1964. Notes on Gender in Modern English. In: Sbornik praci filosoficke fakulty brnenske university A, 12:189-194.
7. VOMLELA, J. 2003. Gender and Animal Nouns in Selected Web Pages Devoted to
8. Animal Keeping and Breeding. In Theory and Practice in English Studies. Volume I.
9. Proceedings from the Seventh Conference of English, American and Canadian Studies, ed. J. Chovanec, 137-142. Brno: Masarykova univerzita.
10. Alisherovna, M. B. (2020). Comparative analysis of the English and Russian proverbs and sayings representating the concept" money". Проблемы современной науки и образования, (4-2 (149)), 43-45.
11. Usmonova, U. H., & Mukhtorova, B. (2023). PAREMIOLOGICAL UNITS OF LANGUAGE. GOLDEN BRAIN, 1(1), 241-244.
12. Абдуразакова, Ш., & Мухторова, Б. (2023). ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ТЕКСТА. Scientific progress, 4(1), 369-373.
13. Mukhtorova, B. (2023). THE LINGUISTIC AND CONCEPTUAL PICTURE OF THE WORLD. Science and innovation, 2(B1), 461-466.
14. Мухторова, Б. А. (2022, September). МОДАЛЛИК КАТЕГОРИЯСИНИНГ ЛИСОНИЙ ҲАМДА МАНТИҚИЙ ТАДҚИҚИ. In INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS" (Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 55-61).

